

Deliverable D1.2

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-STEERS: enable federated data visits and large-scale, cross-border analysis in the life sciences by users across the whole European Research Area (101131096)		
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Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
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02/07/2024	0v2	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Sent to PMO after incorporating internal WP/Hub legal services feedback
02/07/2024	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
10/07/2024	0v4	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	MB comments addressed
10/07/2024	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (hereinafter “the project DMP”) is a mandatory deliverable by the European Commission (EC) that is tailored to the specific project activities and documents the relevant project repositories and how they are managed. In addition, the project DMP considers:

- Comments received as part of the Ethics Summary Report (EthSR) by the EC that were not fully addressed during the Grant Agreement Preparation (Annex 5 of the [Grant Agreement](#)¹).
- Exemplars of the relevant forms used across the project to gather personal data .

The project DMP is a live document that will be reviewed and updated periodically to ensure it remains up to date. The deliverable will have to be revisited particularly in the case that relevant changes are introduced to the Grant Agreement, and in any case, at the end of each reporting period.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1.1: Establishment of the governance structure mobilising the project resources and developing the project guidance, taking diversity into account (Task 1.1 & Task 1.5)	Yes
Objective 1.2: Efficient and effective project execution and monitoring, collecting project key performance indicators (KPIs) and tracking risk, issues, and opportunities to assist the project boards on making informed decisions at all levels (Task 1.2)	Yes
Objective 1.3: Evaluation, development and implementation of the data management plan and sustainability plan (Task 1.3 & Task 1.4)	Yes
Objective 1.4: Increased project management capacity across the ELIXIR Nodes (Task 1.5)	No

3. Introduction

As the purpose of ELIXIR-STEERS is to build capacity for large-scale, cross-border data analysis and for this capacity to be embedded across member states, no research data will be handled during the life cycle of the project. In this deliverable (the Project Data Management Plan) we provide an overview of the project data repository, including how personal data is processed for the purpose of project coordination and management, and address the project Ethics Requirements not already addressed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

- ELIXIR-STEERS Project Repository ([section 4.1](#)) including:
 - Overview of the project data repository

¹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfiWNZJgt6-sv/view

- Access level
- Registration and consent procedures.
- ELIXIR-STEERS Ethics requirements ([section 4.2](#)) not addressed during the Grant Agreement preparation. Including:
 - Data Protection Officer
 - Personal Data Collection
 - Personal Data Transfers
 - Informed consent procedures
 - Further processing of previously collected personal data.
 - Requirement for monitoring of 'emerging issues of AI'

The deliverable has been drafted by the ELIXIR Project Management Office and reviewed by the ELIXIR Legal Services.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 ELIXIR-STEERS Project Repository

4.1.1 Introduction and background

ELIXIR makes use of the legal personality of an intergovernmental organisation, i.e. the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), based on the international treaty “Agreement Establishing the EMBL” see <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/faqs>. ELIXIR also makes use of some of EMBL’s infrastructure and administrative services, provided by EMBL as the host, to the ELIXIR Hub. More general information about EMBL’s legal status can be found here:

<https://www.embl.org/administration/legal-services/>

Among the services provided by EMBL as ELIXIR’s host, ELIXIR uses the EMBL-EBI data repositories to store and share project-related data with project participants. These repositories do not store research data, but administrative project data required to manage, monitor and control the project execution. ELIXIR intends to use one of these repositories also in relation to ELIXIR-STEERS (hereinafter ELIXIR repository) to monitor and control ELIXIR-STEERS project administrative, legal, financial and technical aspects providing a collaborative workspace to generate project deliverables, milestones and manage internal and external communication activities. At the same time, it aims to foster collaboration across project participants. A Google Shared Drive (hosted in the EU) is used as the project repository. Access to the repository is granted, by the Shared Drive manager, i.e. the Project Manager, only once the participants have been registered and verified, see [section 10.1 Project Participants registration form](#).

4.1.2 Project Repository Structure

Top Level Folders	Content
1. Project MASTER File	Master document with details from the project proposal stage: contact lists, effort distribution, lists of deliverables & milestones, GANTT chart etc

	Project monitoring spreadsheet - contains details of all actions, events, deliverables and milestones, along with due dates and templates. It includes the email address of the partners' participants that are relevant for the monitoring and control activities: PIs, Deputies, administrative, financial and legal contacts.
2. Legal Documents	Legal documents pertaining to the project: Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, Description of Action, amendments, contracts etc
3. WPs	Working folders for the WPs, including working templates drafts for each of the WPs deliverables and milestones
4. Deliverables & Milestones	Repository for project deliverables and milestones (those under review and submitted documents)
5. Project meetings, Events & TCs	Details of all project meetings and events (agendas, minutes, slide presentations etc)
6. Periodic Reporting	Financial and periodic reports from all project partners
7. Guidance and Templates	Project handbook, containing guidance pertaining to all aspects of the project (processes, communications, management structure and responsibilities etc) Project templates: deliverables, milestones, agendas minutes, slide presentations etc
8. Project Communications and Outreach Materials	Project branding & style guidelines, press releases, articles, presentations, newsletters etc

4.1.3 Access

All project participants that have registered obtain edit access to the EMBL-EBI-hosted project repository managed by the ELIXIR Project Management Office Team.

4.1.4 Registration (mailing list and repository access)

The registration form is available in [section 10.1](#).

4.2 ELIXIR-STEERS Ethics Requirements

In the following sections we address the Ethics requirements listed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement:

“Activities raising ethical issues must comply with the additional requirements formulated by the ethics panels (including after checks, reviews or audits; see Article 25).

Before starting an action task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities”.

4.2.1 Data protection officer

As indicated under 4.1.1 ELIXIR uses EMBL’s legal personality. EMBL is a distributed intergovernmental organisation and as such benefits from privileges and immunities, such as exemptions from the applicability of national law, in order to allow for the efficient exercise of EMBL’s official functions and to create a uniform legal environment within EMBL across all sites. In the context of data protection, this means that EMBL is not subject to GDPR, which does not apply to international organisations. However, EMBL is still subject to internal data protection rules which reflect the principles and approaches of European data protection law. More information about data protection can be found here <https://www.embl.org/info/data-protection/>.

The Data Protection Officer’s details are provided in the [ELIXIR privacy statement](#) and copied below:

EMBL Data Protection Office

Email: dpo@embl.org

EMBL Heidelberg, Meyerhofstraße 1, DE 69117 Heidelberg, Germany

4.2.2 Personal Data Collection Management and oversight process

The project will be collecting personal data from project participants in the following scenarios:

- During the registration as project participant - required to get access to the project repository.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institutional email address and telephone number, personal email (if needed for access to the repository), ELIXIR Node and institute affiliation, country (of employer institution), project role.
- When registering to attend face to face and virtual meetings: Project meetings (e.g. General Assembly), training events or workshops.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institute affiliation, gender, dietary requirements, accessibility requirements.

The minimum set of information required for running the events is and will be collected. Data collected is kept on the ELIXIR repositories for the period of time requested by the EC in order to allow access to registries in case data needs to be audited.

4.2.3 Personal Data Collected

Details of data being collected in the different scenarios (e.g. participants registration, Kick-off meeting registration, General Assembly meeting registration) can be found in [section 10](#).

According to the Grant Agreement (Annex 1, Part B) “When personal data are collected by project partners, the respective data controllers will adhere to GDPR at all times, following their institutional processes and practices. They will only be stored for the duration needed and will not be used for purposes beyond the effective operation of the ELIXIR-STEERS project”.

4.2.4 Personal Data Transferred from EU to a non-EU country or international organisation

During the project, should personal data be transferred from the EU to a non-EU country or international organisation, confirmation that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation will be included in a following iteration of the DMP.

As indicated under 4.2.1 ELIXIR is subject to EMBL's data protection scheme.

Transfers of participants' personal data to ELIXIR are done in compliance with chapter V of the General Data Protection regulation.

4.2.5 Personal Data Transferred from non-EU country to the EU

No transfer of personal data collected on a non-EU country to an EU country (or another third state) is foreseen in the project activities. Should such a transfer take place during the project, confirmation that such transfers comply with the laws of the country in which the data was collected will be included in a following iteration of the DMP.

4.2.6 Informed consent procedures

Special categories of data (i.e. dietary and accessibility requirements) processed for the overall organisation and participation management of project-related events are processed based on the project participants' consent. The form used to collect consent for processing of special categories of data is included in [section 10.2](#)

4.2.7 Further processing of previously collected personal data

No further processing of previously collected personal data is envisioned in this project. Personal data has been collected using the participant registration form ([see section 10.1](#))

4.2.8 Evaluation the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project

The personal data collected is necessary for the management, monitoring and control of the awarded project.

Considering that the project only processes data of project participants for administrative purposes, no additional risk assessment has been identified as required at the time of producing this deliverable.

4.2.9 Requirement for monitoring of 'emerging issues of AI'

An independent ethics advisor, with specific expertise around the ethics of AI use, will be appointed to the project. This advisor will be invited to join main project meetings, such as the General Assembly, and will produce two deliverable reports, providing advice to the consortium.

5. Results

ELIXIR repositories used to store ELIXIR-STEERS Project related data, including personal data are described in this document. Ethics requirements, as listed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement and in the Ethics Response from the EC, have been addressed in this deliverable.

6. Conclusions

At the time of submission, this deliverable addressed the description of the project repository and how this is managed, addressing also the Ethics requirements listed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement and the EC Proposal Ethics Review (EthSR). The document will be updated as indicated in [section 8](#).

7. Impact

This deliverable provides the basis to collect and manage the personal data indispensable for the project execution.

8. Next Steps

This deliverable will be re-visited in case of modifications on the Grant Agreement and at months 15 and 34 of the project.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Deliverable submitted on time and after conducting the project quality assurance processes defined in D1.1 Project Handbook.

10. Annexes

10.1 ELIXIR-STEERS project participants registration form

Registration of participation in ELIXIR-STEERS

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-03: Consolidation of the RI landscape – Individual support for evolution and long term sustainability of pan-European research infrastructures

The data you enter below will be used for the dissemination of information pertaining to the **grant agreement preparation and** execution of the Horizon Europe ELIXIR-STEERS project (Grant number: 101131096), coordinated by ELIXIR Hub.

Before filling in the form, please read our privacy statement [here](#).

[Sign in to Google](#) to save your progress. [Learn more](#)

* Indicates required question

As a project partner, do you agree with ELIXIR acting on your behalf (as Coordinator) to manage the project? *

- Agree
- Disagree

[Next](#)

[Clear form](#)

Registration of participation in ELIXIR-STEERS

Sign in to [Google](#) to save your progress. [Learn more](#)

* Indicates required question

Participant Contact Details

The information provided below will be kept in a Google Sheet within the project folder so we can add you to our collaborative project repository, to the relevant distribution lists and to send physical documentation if required (e.g. certification of attendance at meetings). In case you can't provide some of the information requested at this point, or prefer not to, we will endeavour to explore other ways to ensure you can still engage and contribute to the project. Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org.

Which ELIXIR Node are you from? *

Choose

First Name *

Your answer

Surname *

Your answer

Institution/ Organisation *

Choose

If 'Other', please provide the name of your Institution/ Organisation.

Your answer

Type of role in the project *

Which option best describes your role in the project?

- Scientific/technical (contribute to a WP)
- Administration
- Finance
- Legal
- Board member

Please provide us with your institutional email address. Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question. *

Your answer

If your institutional email address does not allow you to access Google Shared Drive, please provide an alternative gmail address/email address that allows access (sharing of project documents will be done within Google Drive). Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org if access to Google Drive will be a problem. You may also try using this link which may support you in making your institutional email address compatible with GDrive: <https://support.google.com/accounts/answer/176347?co=GENIE.Platform=Desktop&hl=en>

Your answer

Institution/ Organisation address

Note: This information (including city, country and postcode details) will only be used if we need to send you original documents, e.g. certificate of attendance. If not provided now we will need to request it at a later stage.

A minimum of one person per organisation/institution should provide this information. Please coordinate with your colleagues.

Your answer

Institution/ Organisation Telephone Number

(for urgent communication - e.g. meeting/travel updates)

A minimum of one person per organisation/institution should provide this information.

Please coordinate with your colleagues.

Your answer

[Back](#)[Next](#)[Clear form](#)

Registration of participation in ELIXIR-STEERS

* Indicates required question

Work Packages and other Distribution Lists

Which mailing lists would you like to subscribe to? *

- WP1 - Coordination and support
- WP2 - Implementation of research software best practices through ELIXIR Communities
- WP3 - Infrastructure services to enable adoption and deployment of software best practices
- WP4 - Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training
- WP5 - Communications, outreach, industry and international
- Administration
- Finance
- Legal

Back

Submit

Clear form

10.2 ELIXIR-CONVERGE Kick-off registration form

English

ELIXIR-STEERS Kick-Off Meeting

Short description (max 160 characters). Used for SEO purposes and when advertising Upcoming Events

Welcome to the registration page for the ELIXIR-STEERS Kick-Off Meeting 2024.

The meeting will take place on Wednesday, 7th and Thursday, 8th February (lunch to lunch) in Brussels.

Profile Form

◀ Close

In addition to these fields, the user will always be asked for an e-mail address.

⋮ First name *

⋮ Last name *

Prior to entering your details for registration, please read the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#) which includes information regarding the personal data you provide, the processors we use to deliver events and how you may exercise your rights over your personal data submitted to ELIXIR.

Institute / Organisation *

If you have indicated 'Other',
please add the name of your
institution here

Please indicate which WP or
Board you represent *

If you have indicated 'Other',
please state the initiative or
partner project you are
representing

Gender *

Will you be attending in
person or virtually? *

- In person
- Virtually

Dietary and special requirements

Your dietary and other special requirements are processed based on your consent according to the [ELIXIR Event Privacy Statement](#).

You are not obliged to provide any such data to us. However, without it, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to facilitate your taking part in ELIXIR events by accommodating your dietary or other special needs. Specifically, please be aware that if you have any food allergies but you do not consent to processing of personal data with regards to dietary requirements, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to ensure that catering at the event offers allergy-safe options.

I consent to the processing of
data on my dietary
requirements *

- Yes
- No

View only when I consent to the processing of data on my dietary requirements
= Yes

Please specify

View only when Do you have any dietary requirements: = Other

I consent to the processing of Yes
data on my special No
requirements *

Do you have any special
requirements?

View only when I consent to the processing of data on my special requirements
= Yes

Digital content at ELIXIR events

Occasionally, the ELIXIR Hub may record videos and/or take photographs to promote the event. By attending the event you consent to be video-recorded and/or photographed. You also consent to the further use of the video-recordings and photographs for promotional purposes, i.e. publication of this material on ELIXIR webpages (e.g. ELIXIR public website and intranet) and ELIXIR social media accounts. You may withdraw your consent at any time by emailing us at dataprotection@elixir-europe.org or by informing the event organisers at the reception desk on the day of the event. For further information on data protection and your respective rights, please consult with the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#).

I do not wish to be video-recorded and/or photographed

I understand that it is my responsibility to make myself known to the event organisers at the reception desk.

The [ELIXIR Code of Conduct](#) has been created to ensure that people at ELIXIR events can interact with each other in a respectful and safe environment. It provides ways you can voice your concern if you believe there has been a breach to this Code of Conduct. The ELIXIR Code of Conduct will be in place at this event.

10.3 ELIXIR-CONVERGE Grant Agreement. EthSR Response

EthSR Comment 1: External Independent Ethics Advisor/Board

External Independent Ethics Advisor/Board	
In your opinion, would it be exceptionally necessary to appoint an external independent ethics advisor or an ethics board (with a minimum of three experts) reporting periodically to the Commission/Agency/funding body?	Yes (Ethics Advisor)
Emerging issues of AI need to be monitored	

As mentioned in [Section 4.2.9](#) above, an independent ethics advisor, with specific expertise around the ethics of AI use, will be appointed to the project. At the time of writing of this Deliverable, prospective candidates for the role are being approached.

EthSR Comment 2: General requirements

General requirement applicable to all grants
The beneficiaries must ensure that all ethics issues related to activities in the grant are addressed in compliance with ethical principles, the applicable international and national law, and the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement. This includes the ethics issues identified in this report and any additional ethics issues that may emerge in the course of the grant. In case any substantial new ethics issues arise, beneficiaries should inform the granting authority. For each ethics issue applicable, beneficiaries must follow the guidance provided in the How to complete your ethics self-assessment .

Whilst the scientific focus on ELIXIR-STEERS is on enabling analysis of data through the provision of software and workflows and the collation of best practice recommendations for the community to use, ELIXIR-STEERS itself will not generate or process personal data for the purposes of research at any level. No experiments will be carried out and there are no activities foreseen that will require ethical approval at the institutional level of the partners involved. The project will generate other research assets (e.g. standards guidelines, software, workflow descriptions) none of which are foreseen to contain personal data. These research assets will be published as “open data” in accordance with the data management plan.

Personal data will be collected or generated in the context of what is necessary for effective project management, e.g. mailing lists and registration details of project partners attending project workshops and meetings, including name, dietary preferences and gender (for reporting purposes) - see sections [4.1](#) and [4.2](#) above.